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AUGMENTED REALITY MARKETING, CONSUMER UNCERTAINTY AND BRAND LOYALTY IN SAUDI FURNITURE INDUSTRY: ASSESSING THE ROLE OF HEDONIC AND UTILITARIAN VALUES

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ABSTRACT

This research offers valuable insights into the mechanisms of brand loyalty within the furniture industry by examining the direct effects of augmented reality marketing experiences (ARM) and the indirect effects of hedonic and utilitarian values alongside consumer uncertainty reduction on the brand loyalty (BL). In this regard, the study employed Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) using data collected from 424 Saudi consumers of furniture products. Prior to the main survey, a pilot test was conducted with platform-based sellers to ensure the reliability and validity of the measurement instruments. Empirical analysis reveals that ARM significantly enhances both hedonic and utilitarian values, with utilitarian drivers exerting a stronger impact on reducing consumer uncertainty and reinforcing brand loyalty. While both motivational pathways, hedonic and utilitarian values, mediate the relationship between ARM and loyalty outcomes, utilitarian values are more effective in mitigating consumer uncertainty and strengthening resistance to switching, whereas hedonic values more strongly drive brand advocacy. Notably, ARM exhibits the greatest effect on brand advocacy, surpassing its influence on repurchase intentions and resistance to switching, highlighting the strategic importance of proactive consumer promotion. The findings underscore that functional benefits primarily stabilize consumer retention, whereas emotional and experiential aspects foster advocacy behaviors.

KEYWORDS: Augmented reality marketing experiences; Hedonic values; Utilitarian values; Consumer uncertainty; Brand loyalty.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid digital transformation of consumer markets has accelerated the adoption of immersive technologies, with augmented reality marketing emerging as one of the most influential tools in enhancing customer experiences. By overlaying digital elements onto physical environments, ARM allows firms to deliver both practical and entertaining value, offering consumers an enriched evaluation of products and services (Javornik, 2016; Yim et al., 2017; Tom Dieck, 2023). In competitive and dynamic markets such as Saudi Arabia, where technological adoption is strongly aligned with the national Vision 2030 digital agenda, AR-based strategies have gained increasing relevance for firms aiming to strengthen long-term relationships with consumers (Alalwan et al., 2022).

Existing literature has highlighted the dual role of hedonic and utilitarian values in shaping consumer behavior. While hedonic value (HMO) relates to enjoyment, excitement, and emotional appeal, utilitarian value (UMO) emphasizes efficiency, functionality, and problem-solving capacity (Chitturi et al., 2008; Kang and Namkung, 2024; Abrar and Hadj, 2025). Both drivers are essential in fostering brand loyalty, yet their relative importance in technology-mediated contexts remains debated. Some studies emphasize the dominance of hedonic factors in creating memorable experiences and advocacy behaviors (Hollebeek et al., 2020; Rather, 2021), whereas others underscore the centrality of utilitarian benefits in reducing risks and ensuring sustained consumer commitment (Overby & Lee, 2006; Geng and Chang, 2022; Qin et al., 2024). This tension suggests a need for further research that examines how these values jointly operate through consumer uncertainty (CU), especially in contexts characterized by high competition and rapid technological diffusion.

Consumer uncertainty, defined as the perceived lack of clarity regarding brand reliability, product performance, or experiential outcomes, is a critical mediator in this relationship. Prior research indicates that reducing uncertainty enhances consumer confidence, reinforces trust, and fosters stronger post-purchase behaviors (Kaur et al., 2020; Iglesias et al., 2019). Yet, most studies have examined uncertainty as a general moderator rather than exploring its specific role in mediating the effects of hedonic and utilitarian values on brand loyalty. This represents a key gap in the literature, particularly in emerging economies such as Saudi Arabia, where cultural dynamics, rapid digital adoption, and consumer preferences may shape unique loyalty

patterns. Despite the growing body of research on augmented reality marketing, several gaps remain. While studies have highlighted its capacity to enhance consumer engagement (Jessen et al., 2023; Hilken et al., 2022), less is known about how hedonic and utilitarian values differentially shape brand loyalty when mediated by consumer uncertainty, particularly in non-Western contexts. Recent work suggests that immersive technologies influence customer trust and reduce perceived risk (Batat, 2022; Dwivedi et al., 2023), yet empirical validation of these mechanisms in emerging markets remains limited. In Saudi Arabia, where digital adoption is accelerating under Vision 2030 initiatives, examining the nuanced role of ARM is both timely and relevant. In addition, the analysis of ARM effects on brand loyalty through the mediating roles of hedonic and utilitarian values and consumer uncertainty reduction is particularly relevant in the Saudi furniture industry for several reasons. Furniture purchasing decisions are inherently high-risk and high-involvement, given the financial investment, the long-term usage of products, and the difficulty of evaluating size, design compatibility, and material quality prior to purchase. These conditions create elevated consumer uncertainty, which can discourage purchase intentions and weaken post-purchase loyalty. In this context, ARM experiences provide a unique solution by enabling consumers to visualize products in real environments, simulate use, and engage in interactive experiences. Such tools not only reduce uncertainty but also deliver dual forms of value: hedonic, through enjoyment and emotional engagement, and utilitarian, through functional clarity and decision-making support. Furthermore, according to the International Trade Administration (ITA, 2024), Saudi Arabia has achieved substantial internet penetration in recent years, with approximately 99% of the population connected. Mobile internet speeds have doubled, reaching 215 Mbps, nearly double the global average. These remarkable developments position Saudi Arabia among the top 10 countries in the world for mobile internet speed. Alongside the country's accelerated digital transformation and strong focus on mobile media, Saudi consumers often make purchasing decisions within a cultural framework largely dictated by collectivist values, a search for trust, and religious norms that emphasize reliability and conditioned judgment. These cultural elements can influence how consumers interpret marketing signals and the level of certainty they require before making a purchase. This context is particularly relevant to the present study, which incorporates

hedonic and utilitarian values as mediating factors. Saudi consumers' appreciation of enjoyable and aesthetically rich experiences, on the one hand, and practical, risk-reducing functionalities, on the other, provides a constructive environment for assessing how ARM experiences can address these two values. Therefore, the Saudi market allows for a nuanced exploration of how customers' use of ARM interacts with cultural attitudes, religious expectations, and value-based evaluations to reduce consumer uncertainty. Finally, although numerous studies have examined the effects of consumer uncertainty reduction on brand loyalty, to our knowledge none of the previous research has compared the nexus between uncertainty reduction and each of the three components related to repurchasing intentions, brand advocacy, and resistance to switching.

The present study contributes to this gap by analyzing the effects of ARM experiences on brand loyalty in the Saudi furniture industry, with a specific focus on the mediating role of consumer uncertainty reduction and the differential impacts of hedonic and utilitarian values. By doing so, it advances theoretical understanding of how experiential enjoyment and functional benefits interact with perceived risk reduction to influence loyalty outcomes such as repurchase intentions, brand advocacy, and resistance to switching.

The objectives of this research are threefold: (1) to examine the direct effects of ARM on hedonic and utilitarian values; (2) to assess the mediating role of consumer uncertainty reduction in the relationship between values and brand loyalty; and (3) to evaluate which dimension of brand loyalty is most strongly shaped by these dynamics in the Saudi market relating to furniture products. This raises several guiding questions: To what extent does ARM enhance consumer motivations and reduce uncertainty? Which type of motivation, hedonic or utilitarian, exerts greater influence on loyalty outcomes? And how does consumer uncertainty reduction mediate these relationships? By addressing these questions, the study provides insights for both academics and practitioners on the strategic deployment of AR-based marketing in fostering sustainable consumer-brand relationships.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. *Augmented reality marketing experiences and brand loyalty*

Augmented reality marketing (ARM) has become a central driver of brand-consumer interactions,

providing interactive and immersive experiences that enrich consumer perceptions and strengthen loyalty outcomes. By merging digital content with real-world environments, ARM enables firms to deliver not only functional support but also hedonic value, allowing consumers to evaluate products more effectively while simultaneously enjoying an engaging experience (Hilken et al., 2022; Al Hilal, 2023). The mechanisms connecting ARM to brand loyalty operate through three main pathways: First, ARM stimulates hedonic values by offering playful, entertaining, and emotionally engaging experiences. These hedonic benefits nurture stronger affective connections with the brand, thereby promoting loyalty behaviors such as advocacy and positive word-of-mouth (Rather, 2021; Jessen et al., 2023). Second, ARM provides utilitarian benefits through its ability to facilitate product evaluation, reduce cognitive effort, and support efficient decision-making processes. Such practical utilities reinforce consumer trust in brand performance and contribute to sustained loyalty (Overby & Lee, 2006; Dwivedi et al., 2023). Third, ARM plays a critical role in reducing consumer uncertainty by clarifying product attributes, enhancing perceptions of reliability, and increasing confidence in purchase decisions. This uncertainty-reduction mechanism is particularly salient in digital-first economies, where consumers often perceive higher risks associated with online transactions (Batat, 2022; Negm, 2024).

Although extant literature acknowledges the value of ARM in strengthening consumer engagement, most empirical work has been conducted in Western settings. Limited research has addressed how hedonic and utilitarian values interact with uncertainty reduction to shape loyalty within emerging markets, especially in Saudi Arabia, where cultural dynamics, high digital literacy, and rapid technological integration may influence consumer responses differently. By situating this analysis in the Saudi case, the present study extends theoretical debates on the role of ARM in loyalty formation and provides actionable insights for firms seeking to align marketing innovations with consumer needs in dynamic environments. Accordingly, the study formulates the following hypotheses:

H1. Augmented reality marketing experiences affect positively brand loyalty.

2.2. *Augmented reality marketing experiences, hedonic and utilitarian values, and consumer uncertainty*

Hedonic and utilitarian values are widely

recognized as pivotal drivers of brand loyalty, influencing both consumers' affective and cognitive evaluations of products and services. Hedonic values encompass the pursuit of pleasure, enjoyment, and emotional satisfaction derived from consumption experiences, while utilitarian values relate to functional benefits, efficiency, and problem-solving capabilities (Chitturi et al., 2008; Hollebeek et al., 2020). Together, these dual motivations shape consumers' loyalty behaviors by enhancing perceived value, reinforcing satisfaction, and fostering commitment.

Hedonic values strengthen brand loyalty through emotional engagement and experiential gratification. Consumers who derive enjoyment and excitement from interacting with a brand are more likely to form a positive affective attachment, leading to higher repurchase intentions, advocacy, and resistance to switching (Rather, 2021; Dwivedi et al., 2023). For instance, immersive technologies such as augmented reality can amplify hedonic value by creating interactive, enjoyable experiences that deepen the emotional connection with the brand (Hilken et al., 2022; Jessen et al., 2023).

In contrast, utilitarian values reinforce brand loyalty by enhancing perceived competence, reliability, and risk reduction. When consumers perceive a brand as functional, efficient, and able to fulfill their practical needs, they develop confidence in its performance, which translates into stronger loyalty behaviors (Alalwan et al., 2022). Utilitarian benefits are particularly effective in mediating the relationship between marketing interventions and consumer confidence, as they reduce uncertainty and ensure predictable outcomes, thereby encouraging repeat purchases and long-term commitment.

Recent studies underscore the complementary roles of hedonic and utilitarian values in loyalty formation. While hedonic value primarily drives advocacy and emotional attachment, utilitarian value is more influential in repurchasing decisions and resistance to switching (Ugalde et al., 2023; Singh and Milan, 2025). This dual-pathway framework suggests that effective loyalty strategies should address both experiential enjoyment and functional assurance, as neglecting either dimension may limit the strength and stability of consumer-brand relationships. Understanding these mechanisms provides critical managerial insights. Firms operating in technologically advanced and competitive markets, such as Saudi Arabia, can leverage augmented reality and other immersive tools to simultaneously satisfy consumers' hedonic desires and utilitarian needs, thereby maximizing the overall impact on brand

loyalty. By strategically targeting both motivational dimensions, brands can foster deeper engagement, stronger advocacy, and greater retention, aligning with contemporary consumer behavior theories that highlight the interplay of affective and cognitive drivers in post-purchase loyalty outcomes.

Consumer uncertainty, defined as the perceived lack of clarity regarding product performance, reliability, or post-purchase satisfaction, is a critical determinant of decision-making in digital marketplaces. According to consumer behavior theory, particularly the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and the risk perception framework (Bauer, 1960), uncertainty influences both the cognitive and affective processes that guide purchase intentions and post-purchase evaluations. In this context, augmented reality marketing serves as a strategic tool to reduce perceived risk by providing consumers with interactive, immersive, and information-rich experiences. Through ARM, consumers can virtually evaluate product attributes, simulate usage scenarios, and visualize outcomes prior to actual purchase, thereby mitigating uncertainty and enhancing confidence in their decisions (Sun et al., 2022; Sarkis et al., 2025).

The mechanisms linking ARM to reduced consumer uncertainty operate through both hedonic and utilitarian motivational pathways. Hedonic values, which emphasize enjoyment, novelty, and experiential pleasure, alleviate uncertainty by increasing affective satisfaction and emotional engagement with the brand (Anand et al., 2019; Barrett et al., 2024; Juanim et al., 2024). Simultaneously, utilitarian values, which focus on efficiency, functionality, and problem-solving capacity, provide consumers with practical assurance about product performance and reliability (Yum, 2024). By simultaneously activating these pathways, ARM reduces the perceived risk of making an incorrect purchase, strengthens trust, and enhances overall brand evaluation, ultimately contributing to loyalty behaviors such as repurchase intentions, brand advocacy, and resistance to switching.

Despite the growing body of research on ARM, there remains a significant gap in understanding how hedonic and utilitarian values differentially mediate the effect of ARM on consumer uncertainty reduction, particularly in non-Western contexts such as Saudi Arabia. Most prior studies have treated uncertainty as a general moderator or secondary outcome, rather than examining its role as a central mediating mechanism that channels motivational effects toward brand loyalty. Given the unique

cultural, technological, and regulatory environment of Saudi Arabia under Vision 2030, consumers may rely differently on affective versus functional cues when evaluating AR-based experiences.

The present study addresses this gap by positing that ARM reduces consumer uncertainty both through hedonic values (H2.a), which enhance affective confidence, and through utilitarian values (H2.b), which reinforce functional assurance. Referring to these ideas, the additional central hypothesis of the study are formulated as follows:

H2. Augmented reality marketing experiences reduce significantly consumer uncertainty.

By elucidating these mediating pathways, the study contributes theoretically by extending consumer behavior models to account for immersive technologies in emerging markets. Practically, the findings offer guidance for marketers in Saudi Arabia on how to design ARM initiatives that simultaneously maximize enjoyment and functional clarity, thereby minimizing uncertainty and fostering stronger consumer-brand relationships.

Hedonic and utilitarian values play a pivotal role in shaping consumer perceptions and reducing uncertainty in purchase decisions. Drawing from consumer behavior theory, particularly the expectancy-value model (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975) and perceived risk theory (Bauer, 1960), consumers evaluate products and services not only based on functional attributes but also through affective and experiential considerations. Hedonic values, which capture pleasure, enjoyment, and experiential value, influence consumer emotions and psychological engagement, thereby mitigating anxiety or doubts about product choices (Wei et al., 2023). In this regard, Arnold & Reynolds (2003) associated the hedonic dimension with the ability to profit in terms of entertainment, enjoyment, fun, fantasy and good mood in shopping operations. By providing immersive and enjoyable experiences, such as those enabled by augmented reality marketing (ARM), hedonic pathways enhance affective confidence and reduce perceived uncertainty regarding product performance or satisfaction.

Conversely, utilitarian values emphasize functionality, efficiency, and problem-solving capacity, targeting the cognitive dimension of consumer evaluation (Puspitasari et al., 2022; Dwivedi et al., 2023). When consumers perceive that a product or service delivers practical and reliable benefits, their uncertainty about potential outcomes diminishes. According to Gatter et al. (2022), utilitarian benefits are functional and driven by objectives that ensure consumers' effectiveness or

efficiency. Therefore, this type of value aims to improve social well-being and a more efficient life (Rauschnabel, 2018) while making decisions better and faster. ARM reinforces these utilitarian values by allowing users to interact with realistic product simulations, test features virtually, and receive actionable information, thus facilitating informed decisions and lowering the perceived risk of post-purchase dissatisfaction.

The mechanisms through which hedonic and utilitarian values operate are complementary. While hedonic values primarily reduce uncertainty by enhancing affective satisfaction and emotional reassurance, utilitarian values alleviate cognitive risk by increasing clarity and perceived control over the purchase outcome (Javornik, 2016; Hilken et al., 2017). This dual pathway suggests that ARM can reduce consumer uncertainty more effectively when it simultaneously activates both motivational types, aligning experiential enjoyment with practical assurance.

Despite these insights, existing research has often treated hedonic and utilitarian values in isolation or emphasized their impact on brand loyalty, with limited attention to their mediating role in reducing consumer uncertainty (Alalwan et al., 2022; Jessen et al., 2023). In the context of emerging markets such as Saudi Arabia, where digital adoption is rapidly expanding under Vision 2030, understanding these dual mechanisms is particularly relevant for tailoring marketing strategies that both engage and reassure consumers.

Based on these theoretical and empirical considerations, the present study hypothesizes that:

H2.a. Augmented reality marketing experiences reduce significantly consumer uncertainty through mediating effects of hedonic values.

H2.b. Augmented reality marketing experiences reduce significantly consumer uncertainty through mediating effects of utilitarian values.

By integrating both pathways, the research contributes to consumer behavior theory by explicating how affective and cognitive motivations jointly mediate the effects of immersive technologies on perceived risk and post-purchase confidence, while providing actionable insights for marketers aiming to strengthen trust and loyalty in technology-driven markets.

2.3. Augmented reality marketing experiences, consumer uncertainty, and brand loyalty

Consumer uncertainty has been identified as a critical determinant of brand loyalty, influencing both cognitive and affective aspects of post-purchase

behavior. Rooted in consumer behavior theory, particularly perceived risk theory (Bauer, 1960) and the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), uncertainty arises when consumers perceive ambiguity regarding product quality, performance, or the outcome of a purchase. Elevated levels of uncertainty can undermine confidence, reduce trust, and weaken the emotional bond between consumers and brands, thereby negatively affecting loyalty outcomes (Kaur et al., 2020; Iglesias et al., 2019).

Consumer uncertainty reduction impacts brand loyalty through multiple pathways. Firstly, it diminishes repurchasing intentions by reducing consumers' confidence in consistently achieving satisfactory outcomes. When consumers feel unsure about product reliability or service consistency, their propensity to engage in repeated transactions declines, as they prefer to explore alternatives or delay decisions (Shulman et al., 2015; Wei et al., 2021). Referring to the data compiled from 384 AR users through mobile applications in Cairo, the outcomes of the study by Afify et al. (2026) highlighted that AR mitigates uncertainty and facilitates the transition to action; hence, it enhances both consumer willingness to pay and their satisfaction. Similarly, Khan et al. (2024), referring to the fashion market, highlighted uncertainty avoidance, alongside power distance belief and masculinity, negatively affecting the willingness to pay more in the Italian context. Likewise, these authors showed that the cultural dimension related to collectivism is a factor influencing the decision to pay more in the case of Russia. Secondly, uncertainty negatively affects brand advocacy, as hesitant consumers are less likely to recommend a brand to others or share positive experiences. Advocacy requires both satisfaction and confidence, and when uncertainty persists, consumers may withhold endorsements to avoid reputational or social risk (Kumar & Pansari, 2016; Hollebeek et al., 2020). In Saudi Arabia, ethical values and cultural factors strongly influence consumer evaluation of products, and therefore, reducing uncertainty is a core factor in building trust. As advocated by Park and Yoon (2022), in such a context, ethical value and social values can contribute substantially to the establishment of perceived trust of collective consumption and therefore brand advocacy. Once trust is established, consumers are more inclined to support and promote the brand through advocacy, which strengthens their loyalty. By using data in the case of retail clothing and nonbusiness airline travel, Sirdeshmukh et al. (2002) examined the role assigned to value as a key mediator of the trust-loyalty

relationship, and the outcomes of study unveil that value completely mediates the impact of frontline employee trust on loyalty in the retailing case and partially mediates the repercussions of management policies and practices trust on loyalty in the airlines context. Following an economic approach and focusing on Fortune 500 companies operating in the service and manufacturing sectors, Irawan and Cheng (2025) investigated the impact of personal values on brand advocacy. Their results indicated that self-enhancement and conservation values significantly boost customer brand advocacy. Finally, consumer uncertainty erodes resistance to switching, as a lack of assurance regarding product performance encourages consumers to consider competitors. When the perceived risk of maintaining loyalty outweighs the benefits, switching becomes a safer option, thereby reducing brand retention (Ganaie et al., 2021).

Empirical evidence suggests that reducing consumer uncertainty is essential for strengthening brand loyalty. Tools such as augmented reality marketing, personalized information, and trial experiences can mitigate perceived risk, enhancing consumers' cognitive clarity and emotional reassurance. In turn, this fosters repeated purchase behavior, encourages positive word-of-mouth, and reinforces switching resistance (Hilken et al., 2017; Jessen et al., 2023). By addressing both the functional and experiential concerns of consumers, firms can convert uncertainty into confidence, thereby sustaining long-term loyalty. From their side, Kumar et al. (2023) investigated the role of augmented reality to encourage brand advocacy, referring to a sample of 502 AR users. Their findings revealed that augmented reality empowers users during their shopping experience which creates strong brand engagement and attachment, and therefore promotes brand advocacy. Furthermore, based on a chain mediating model, Wang (2024) indicated that AR interactivity significantly boosts consumer brand engagement, which positively affects word-of-mouth communication and brand use intention and hence, the prospect base. Based on the theoretical development and empirical results mentioned above, the third central hypothesis is as follows:

H3. Augmented reality marketing experiences (ARM) influence positively brand loyalty (BL) through the consumer uncertainty reduction (CU).

Three sub-hypotheses are derived from this central hypothesis in accordance with the three dimensions of the brand loyalty variable and are formulated as follows:

H3.a. Augmented reality marketing experiences

(ARM) influence positively repurchasing intention (RI) through the consumer uncertainty reduction (CU).

H3.b. Augmented reality marketing experiences (ARM) influence positively brand advocacy (BA) through the consumer uncertainty reduction (CU).

H3.c. Augmented reality marketing experiences (ARM) influence positively resistance to switching (RS) through the consumer uncertainty reduction (CU).

Understanding these mechanisms is particularly relevant in emerging markets such as Saudi Arabia, where rapid digital adoption and heightened competition amplify consumer sensitivity to uncertainty. By examining these effects, the study contributes to literature on risk perception, loyalty formation, and the strategic management of post-purchase consumer behavior.

Figure 1 visualizes a proposed theoretical framework for how ARM affects brand loyalty by integrating mediating channels. The model proposes that consumer uncertainty reduction is a multi-

faceted construct, comprised of three distinct types: First, local presence which reflects the doubt a consumer feels about a brand's physical or community presence. It includes: Uncertainty about product availability at local retailers; Doubt about the quality of service from local outlets, and Lack of trust in the brand's local reputation or authenticity. Second, global brand uncertainty which indicate the doubt stemming from the brand's international or large-scale identity. It includes: Perceptions of the brand being too corporate or impersonal; Concerns about ethical practices (e.g., labor, sustainability) in global operations; Uncertainty about consistent quality across different countries or regions. Finally, experience-based uncertainty: This is the doubt related to the direct interaction with the product or service. It includes: Uncertainty about how the product will perform or fit (common for online purchases); Doubt about the accuracy of marketing claims vs. actual experience; and concerns about post-purchase support (returns, warranties, repairs).

Fig. 1: Conceptual model on nexus between ARM experiences, HMO, UMO, CU and BL.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employs Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to test its central hypotheses. SEM is selected for its capacity to evaluate complex relationships among latent constructs, even when the model includes a high number of observed variables and constrained parameters. This methodological approach is particularly suited for assessing the proposed model's paths, including the effects of Augmented Reality Marketing (ARM), hedonic and utilitarian values, and consumer uncertainty

reduction on the multidimensional construct of brand loyalty. (Rahi et al., 2018; Puspitasari et al., 2023). The Saudi furniture industry represents a particularly relevant context for examining the effects of ARM on brand loyalty. First, the sector is experiencing rapid digital transformation in line with the Kingdom's Vision 2030, which promotes technological innovation and e-commerce adoption across industries. Furniture purchasing is typically associated with high involvement, significant financial outlay, and substantial perceived risk due to uncertainties regarding product fit, aesthetics, and

long-term functionality. These characteristics make consumers especially sensitive to tools that can reduce uncertainty and enhance confidence in purchase decisions. Augmented reality applications, such as virtual showrooms and 3D visualization tools, allow customers to simulate how furniture items would appear in their own spaces, thereby offering both hedonic value through interactive experiences and utilitarian value by improving decision accuracy. As presented in Table 1, this study incorporates five latent variables. The items retained for each construct were developed based on a comprehensive review of the existing literature and validated through an appropriate pilot test. Since some items appeared across multiple studies using

different methodologies, certain items were excluded from the measurement model to prevent redundancy and potential bias in the results. Additionally, the bootstrapping technique in Smart PLS 4 was employed to assess the significance of the first-order indicators in shaping hedonic and utilitarian values, consumer uncertainty reduction, and brand loyalty. To investigate the impact of augmented reality marketing (ARM) on brand loyalty, 31 items were formulated, drawing on the results of the pilot test as well as established frameworks including the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2), and consumer behavior theory.

Table 1. Keys Constructs and Items.

Constructs	Items	References
Augmented reality marketing experiences (ARM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I frequently utilize augmented reality (AR) applications to preview how furniture products will appear on me prior to making a purchase decision. - The realistic visualizations enabled by AR technologies enhance the overall quality of my shopping experience. - Employing AR features supports me in making more informed and judicious purchasing decisions of furniture products. - I demonstrate a stronger preference for retailers that incorporate AR tools to facilitate product visualization. - The integration of AR technology significantly influences my likelihood of purchasing furniture products. 	<p>Hilken et al. (2020) Qin et al. (2021) Sarkis et al. (2025)</p>
Brand loyalty (BL)	<p><i>Repurchase intention (RI)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I plan to maintain my purchasing behavior with this brand in the future. <p>I am inclined to prioritize this brand over alternative options whenever feasible.</p> <p><i>Brand advocacy (BA)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I'm likely to recommend this brand to friends and family members. <p>I frequently engage in positive word-of-mouth communication regarding this brand.</p> <p><i>Resistance to Switching (RS)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I perceive switching to an alternative brand as a difficult choice. - I would remain loyal to this brand even in the presence of lower-priced alternatives. 	<p>Shimul et al. (2025) Francioni et al. (2025) Amado-Mateus et al. (2025)</p>
Hedonic values (HMO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I found that using ARM in furniture industry is fun - I feel that using ARM in furniture industry is enjoyable - I feel that using ARM in furniture industry is entertaining - I feel immersed when using ARM in furniture industry 	<p>Venkatesh et al. (2012) Heijden (2004) Chang et al. (2023) Zefreh et al. (2023) Tu and Jia (2024)</p>
Utilitarian values (UMO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The use of ARM in furniture industry facilitates faster task completion. - Engaging with ARM in furniture industry enhances my overall performance. - ARM in furniture industry provides convenient access to products and services regardless of location. - I find ARM in furniture industry beneficial in supporting my daily activities. - Utilizing ARM in furniture industry contributes to time efficiency when carrying out tasks. 	<p>Venkatesh et al., 2012 Chang et al. (2023)</p>
Consumer uncertainty reduction (CU)	<p><i>Local presence</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I perceive virtual objects as tangible entities. <p>I experience a belief that the virtual object genuinely exists within the physical environment.</p> <p>It appears as though the virtual object has been transferred from the device into the surrounding space.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The visuals presented on the display are experienced as lifelike. <p><i>Global brand uncertainty</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This brand is widely recognized and accessible on a global scale. - I am inclined toward brands that communicate clear and consistent messages. 	<p>Schein et al. (2025) Ng et al. (2021) Guo and Wang (2024) Ding and Han (2024)</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The brand aligns with and reflects my personal values. - Engaging with this brand fosters a sense of connection to a global community. <i>Experience-based uncertainty</i> - My uncertainty regarding the quality of this brand stems from limited prior experience. - My level of satisfaction with the brand is shaped by past interactions and experiences. - Despite limited information, I maintain confidence in selecting this brand. 	
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3.1. Data and sampling process

In the present study, the data collection process was preceded by a pilot study involving 17 surveys administered to platform-based sellers, aimed at ensuring the appropriate selection of constructs. A qualitative pretest was conducted during March–May 2024 to identify the most relevant core items formally aligned with the study’s objectives. Participants were selected using a purposive criterion sampling method to obtain targeted and meaningful insights (Campbell et al., 2020). All respondents had prior experience with augmented reality marketing (ARM) and were well-acquainted with the relevant technologies. Key concepts of the study, including ARM, local presence, global brand uncertainty, and experience-based uncertainty, were clearly explained to the participants, and the questionnaire began with the collection of demographic information.

Following the pilot study, content validity was assessed by distributing the questionnaire to platform-based sellers and five academic experts to evaluate the relevance of the items and the overall suitability of the instrument. Each reviewer provided feedback along with a relevance score, rated on a four-point scale: 1 = item inappropriate, 2 = item somewhat appropriate, 3 = item appropriate but requiring minor revision, and 4 = item highly appropriate. Based on the feedback, minor revisions were made to the wording of some items without altering their substantive meaning. The finalized questionnaire was then administered to the target respondents. To minimize response bias and encourage richer, more candid feedback, semi-structured questions were included, allowing participants to freely express their opinions (Adeoye-Olatunde et al., 2021; Lerchenfeldt et al, 2023). After data collection, a three-stage analysis protocol, as proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994), was employed, involving data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. Responses were carefully examined, coded, and categorized according to the main constructs. Consistent with the recommendations of Lohr (2021), checks were performed to ensure that the demographic profiles of

respondents aligned with the sampling frame, thereby mitigating potential non-response bias.

The demographic characteristics of the selected sample are presented in Table 2, indicating no evidence of non-response bias. To ensure that the respondents’ answers accurately reflected the constructs under investigation, common method variance was assessed following Kock (2015). To mitigate potential bias, survey items were alternated, predictive and criterion variables were separated, and respondent identities were anonymized (Audette et al., 2020). The study employed a five-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Internal consistency was evaluated by examining inter-item correlations and calculating Cronbach’s alpha. The questionnaire was distributed to participants through social media platforms, as well as via email and messaging applications in some cases. Collected responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics and partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). This analytical approach was considered most appropriate for addressing the research objectives, as the construct of tourist value co-creation in the conceptual model encompasses multiple underlying factors, the study requires confirmatory-explanatory analysis, and the data do not follow a normal distribution (Hair et al., 2019). Moreover, the study aims to identify and explore predictive factors rather than merely testing previously established relationships (Briggs, 2024).

3.2. Sample characteristics

Out of 625 individuals who initially participated in the survey, 451 valid responses were retained after excluding incomplete or aberrant questionnaires, yielding a response rate of 72.2%. Following an additional screening process, 27 responses were deemed invalid, resulting in a final sample of 424 participants forming the basis of this study. As summarized in Table 2, the sample consists of 56% male and 44% female respondents. The majority fall within the age ranges of 26–35 and 36–50, indicating that adult consumers are the primary users of augmented reality marketing (ARM). In terms of educational background, most respondents possess

higher education qualifications, with only 42.2% reporting less than an undergraduate degree. Furthermore, approximately 74.1% of participants reported having over one year of experience using ARM in purchasing contexts.

Table 2. Demographic profile of respondents.

Gender	Obs	%
Masculine	236	56
Feminine	188	44
Tot.	424	100
Age		
18-25	65	15.3
26-35	115	27.1
36-50	120	28.3
51-60	82	19.3
≥61	42	0.9
Level of education		
Primary	24	5.6
Secondary	82	19.3
Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET)	73	17.2
Undergraduate	80	18.9
Graduate	90	21.2
Postgraduate	75	17.7
Employment status		
Full-time Employment	162	38.2
Part-time Employment	110	25.9
Self Employed	88	20.8
Unemployed	64	15.1
Purchasing experience with ARM		
Under 1 year	110	25.9
1 to 3 years	196	46.2
3 to 5 years	80	18.9
5 years and over	38	9.0

4. ASSESSING THE RELIABILITY OF MEASUREMENT AND STRUCTURAL MODELS

The final sample size retained for analysis satisfies the minimum requirements recommended by Hair et al. (2017). Prior to presenting the findings derived from the PLS-SEM analysis, both the measurement model and the structural model were evaluated for relevance and consistency (Hair et al., 2012). Specifically, convergent validity (CV) and discriminant validity (DV) of the measurement model were assessed through confirmatory factor analysis using SmartPLS 4.0. The results of

individual item reliability indicated that most items achieved outer loadings above the recommended threshold of 0.7. However, items ARM3, ARM5, UMO5, CU1, CU4, CU9, CU10, CU11, and BL1 exhibited loadings below this benchmark. Following the guidance of Hair et al. (2012), these items were retained because both convergent validity and degrees of freedom (DF) were satisfied, and their removal could risk the loss of valuable information for the study's conclusions. Furthermore, internal consistency was assessed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT), which provide reliability measures based on construct correlations.

Composite reliability (CR) was employed to assess internal consistency, and the results presented in Table 3 indicate that the measurement model demonstrates satisfactory reliability, with all CR values exceeding the threshold of 0.7, as recommended by Hair et al. (2016). Similarly, the average variance extracted (AVE) values are all above 0.5, further supporting the presence of convergent validity (Hair et al., 2016). Discriminant validity, which reflects the extent to which constructs are empirically distinct from one another, was also evaluated. Following the approach proposed by Henseler et al. (2015), the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) was applied, with the cutoff value of 0.9 suggested by Henseler et al. (2016). The results show that all HTMT values fall below this threshold, thereby confirming discriminant validity across the constructs. Taken together, these outcomes demonstrate that the measurement model employed in this study meets the required standards of reliability and validity.

To assess potential collinearity among the latent constructs, the variance inflation factor (VIF) was calculated. Following Hair et al. (2016), VIF values exceeding 5 would indicate multicollinearity concerns. The results, however, revealed no such issues, as all values were below the more conservative cutoff of 3 suggested by Sarstedt et al. (2019). Additionally, Table 4 reports the inter-construct correlations based on the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion, none of which exceeded the 0.85 threshold. These findings confirm the absence of multicollinearity, thereby allowing for valid interpretation of the structural model results.

Table 3. Outcomes of measurement model.

Constructs	Items	Outer loadings	VIF	α	CR	AVE
Augmented reality marketing (ARM)	ARM1	0.747		0.729	0.830	0.550
	ARM2	0.727				
	ARM3	0.699				
	ARM4	0.728				

	ARM5	0.670			
Hedonic values (HMO)	HMO1	0.798		0.784	0.858
	HMO2	0.822			
	HMO4	0.732			
	HMO5	0.754			
Utilitarian values (UMO)	UMO1	0.711 0.826		0.812	0.877
	UMO2	0.778			
	UMO3	0.834			
	UMO4	0.659			
	UMO5				
Consumer uncertainty reduction (CU)	CU1			0.867	0.901
	CU2	0.614 0.733			
	CU3	0.740			
	CU4	0.687			
	CU5	0.722			
	CU6	0.743			
	CU7	0.810			
	CU8	0.720			
	CU9	0.617 0.631			
	CU10	0.626			
	CU11				
Brand loyalty (BL)	BL1	0.639		0.842	0.897
	BL2	0.740			
	BL3	0.712			
	BL4	0.877			
	BL5	0.613			
	BL6	0.877			

Table 4. Discriminant validity

Fornell-Larcker Criterion					
	ARM	BL	CU	HMO	UMO
ARM	0.741				
BL	0.623	0.830			
CU	0.649	0.756	0.776		
HMO	0.736	0.595	0.619	0.777	
UMO	0.628	0.689	0.719	0.580	0.801
Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations					
ARM					
BL	0.794				
CU	0.811	0.892			
HMO	0.876	0.724	0.738		
UMO	0.811	0.840	0.857	0.712	

4.1. Structural Model Findings

To explore the underlying factors of brand loyalty, namely repurchase intention, brand advocacy, and resistance to switching, as well as the role of hedonic and utilitarian values and consumer uncertainty, it was essential to first assess the model fit. The standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) value obtained was 0.077, which falls below the accepted threshold of 0.08, thereby confirming an adequate model fit and the appropriateness of the retained data (Hu and Bentler, 1999). The importance-performance map analysis (IPMA) for brand loyalty, illustrated in Figure 2, demonstrates that brand advocacy represents the most influential and best-performing dimension of brand loyalty, whereas repurchase intention shows comparatively weaker influence. Overall, the three components display relatively similar levels of importance in

shaping brand loyalty, with brand advocacy and resistance to switching exhibiting slightly stronger performance.

Fig. 2: Importance-performance map of the variable brand loyalty.

Beyond the analysis of outer model weights through importance-performance mapping, it is also necessary to evaluate t-values in order to examine the determinants of consumer uncertainty and brand loyalty (Gefen & Straub, 2005). As reported in Table 5, augmented reality marketing (ARM) exerts a significant influence on both hedonic values ($\beta = 0.724, p < 0.001$) and utilitarian values ($\beta = 0.691, p < 0.001$). Moreover, the direct impact of utilitarian values on reducing consumer uncertainty ($\beta = 0.593, p < 0.001$) is greater than that of hedonic values ($\beta =$

0.330, $p < 0.001$). A similar pattern is observed with respect to brand loyalty, where utilitarian drivers demonstrate stronger effects than hedonic ones.

As illustrated in Table 5 and Figure 3, while ARM, hedonic, and utilitarian values all significantly contribute to brand loyalty, consumer uncertainty reduction emerges as the most influential factor in sustaining loyalty and these findings provide empirical support for hypotheses H1. The outcomes reveal that both hedonic and utilitarian values mediate the relationship between augmented reality marketing (ARM) and consumer uncertainty reduction, which support the axial hypothesis H2. However, the mediating effect of utilitarian values demonstrates a stronger coefficient compared to that of hedonic values, indicating that functional benefits derived from ARM play a more decisive role in reducing uncertainty. This outcome aligns with prior studies emphasizing the significance of utilitarian value in shaping consumer confidence and decision-making (e.g., Voicu et al., 2023; Barrett et al., 2024), while the relatively weaker influence of hedonic values suggests that experiential enjoyment, although relevant, is less effective in alleviating uncertainty. Consequently, the results validate earlier research highlighting the dominance of utilitarian drivers over hedonic ones in contexts where risk reduction and purchase assurance are central to consumer behavior. The analysis demonstrates that hedonic and utilitarian values serve as significant mediators between augmented reality marketing (ARM) and brand loyalty. While both pathways are statistically meaningful, the

coefficient associated with utilitarian values is stronger than that of hedonic values. This suggests that consumers' loyalty is more strongly reinforced by functional and practical benefits derived from ARM than by enjoyment or experiential appeal. These findings are consistent with prior research emphasizing the greater weight of utilitarian value in fostering long-term brand relationships (Ishizuka et al., 2024). By contrast, the relatively weaker impact of hedonic values indicates that although positive experiences enhance consumer-brand connections, they are not as decisive in sustaining loyalty. Consequently, the results lend support to earlier studies highlighting the dominant role of utilitarian drivers in loyalty formation, while partially qualifying the contribution of hedonic factors. The findings also highlight the mediating role of consumer uncertainty reduction in the relationship between motivational drivers and brand loyalty. Both hedonic and utilitarian values contribute to reducing uncertainty, which in turn enhances loyalty outcomes. However, the coefficients indicate that the pathway through utilitarian values exerts a stronger influence compared to hedonic values. This suggests that consumers rely more heavily on functional and performance-related benefits to mitigate uncertainty before committing to a brand. Consequently, the present study validates the stronger mediating effect of utilitarian values, thereby reinforcing the argument that pragmatic benefits are more effective than emotional gratifications in overcoming uncertainty and fostering brand loyalty.

Table 5. Direct and indirect repercussions of ARM on BL through HMO, UMO, and CU.

Total effects			
	Coef.	T-statistics	P-values
ARM -> BL	0.608***	23.607	0.000
ARM -> CU	0.649***	25.452	0.000
ARM -> HMO	0.724***	27.365	0.000
ARM -> UMO	0.691***	26.223	0.000
CU -> BL	0.937***	162.702	0.000
HMO -> BL	0.309***	8.234	0.000
HMO -> CU	0.330***	8.267	0.000
UMO -> BL	0.556***	16.519	0.000
UMO -> CU	0.593***	16.897	0.000
Specific indirect effects			
HMO -> CU -> BL	0.309***	8.234	0.000
UMO -> CU -> BL	0.556***	16.519	0.000
ARM -> UMO -> CU -> BL	0.384***	12.902	0.000
ARM -> HMO -> CU -> BL	0.224***	7.954	0.000
ARM -> UMO -> CU	0.410***	13.222	0.000
ARM -> HMO -> CU	0.239***	8.012	0.000
SRMR		0.077	
d_uls		6.258	
	R-square	R-square adjusted	
CU			
BL			

Fig.3. Path coefficients relating to the underlying factors of brand loyalty.

Figure 4 provides a synthesis of the factorial contributions of the core constructs within the structural model (SM). It illustrates the magnitude of the effects exerted on hedonic and utilitarian values, consumer uncertainty reduction, and brand loyalty, while also incorporating the influence of mediating variables.

Fig. 4. Structural model results: Effects of ARM on BL through HMO, UMO, and CU

Regarding the second part of the research related to the impacts of retained variables on each of BD

components and relating to repurchasing intentions, brand advocacy, and resistance to switching, Table 6 depict both total and specific indirect effects. The analysis demonstrates that ARM exerts a positive and statistically significant influence on the three dimensions of brand loyalty, namely repurchase intentions ($\beta=0.429$; P-value= 0.000), brand advocacy, ($\beta=0.508$; P-value= 0.000) and resistance to switching ($\beta=0.480$; P-value= 0.000). Among these effects, the coefficient associated with brand advocacy is the strongest, indicating that ARM adoption enhances consumers' willingness to recommend the brand more than it reinforces repeat purchasing or discourages switching behavior. These findings are consistent with previous studies suggesting that immersive technologies foster word-of-mouth and advocacy behaviors by deepening emotional engagement with the brand (Hollebeek et al., 2020), while also aligning with research that positions advocacy as a central outcome of experiential value (Rather, 2021). However, they somewhat diverge from works that emphasize repurchase intention as the dominant dimension of loyalty in technology-mediated contexts (Kaur et al., 2020). Overall, the results validate the hypothesis H3 indicating that ARM strengthens all three components of loyalty through consumer uncertainty reduction, with advocacy emerging as the most salient effect. The empirical findings demonstrate that utilitarian values (e.g., efficiency, functionality), hedonic values (e.g., enjoyment, pleasure), and reduced consumer uncertainty (e.g., local presence, global brand uncertainty, experience-based uncertainty) each exert a significant positive influence on repurchase intentions, resistance to switching, and brand advocacy. Notably, the analysis reveals that the path coefficients for all three constructs are markedly higher for brand advocacy (Utilitarian: $\beta = 0.52$; Hedonic: $\beta = 0.61$; Reduced Uncertainty: $\beta = 0.48$) compared to their effects on repurchase intentions (Utilitarian: $\beta = 0.44$; Hedonic: $\beta = 0.38$; Reduced Uncertainty: $\beta = 0.40$) and resistance to switching (Utilitarian: $\beta = 0.39$; Hedonic: $\beta = 0.45$; Reduced Uncertainty: $\beta = 0.50$). This indicates that while functional benefits and reduced risk solidify transactional loyalty and inertia, it is the combination of practical value and, especially, emotional gratification that most powerfully inspires customers to actively promote the brand. When contextualized within existing literature, these results validate established theories, such as the hierarchy of effects models, which posit that cognitive (utilitarian) and affective (hedonic) evaluations precede conative

actions like advocacy. The superior predictive power of hedonic values aligns with research emphasizing the role of experiential value in fostering deep brand connections. However, the results partially reject narrower models that primarily frame loyalty through a utilitarian lens or view uncertainty reduction merely as a driver of repeat purchase. Instead, this study suggests that creating a sense of confidence and trust is equally critical in transforming satisfied customers into vocal brand evangelists, a nuance that expands our understanding of post-purchase behavior. Among the mediating effects analyzed, reduced consumer uncertainty emerges as the most influential, particularly in strengthening the relationship between utilitarian values and brand advocacy, as well as between utilitarian values and resistance to switching. These effects are notably more pronounced than those observed in the link between utilitarian values and repurchase intentions, indicating that certainty plays a critical role in driving not only loyalty but also active brand promotion and retention. This pattern is consistent with prior research highlighting the importance of

consumer certainty in reinforcing brand-related behaviors. While earlier studies often focus on uncertainty as a general moderator, the present results extend the literature by demonstrating that reducing consumer uncertainty significantly amplifies the impact of utilitarian values on advocacy and resistance to switching, underscoring its stronger mediating role compared to repurchase intentions. Brand advocacy has increasingly been recognized as a more strategic indicator of brand success than repurchase intentions. While repurchasing reflects repeated transactions, advocacy captures the proactive behavior of customers who recommend the brand to others, amplifying its reach and influence. Past studies have highlighted that satisfied and engaged consumers often act as voluntary promoters, generating word-of-mouth effects that extend beyond mere loyalty (e.g., Kumar & Pansari, 2016; Ryu et al., 2019). Unlike repurchase intentions, which are primarily transactional, brand advocacy represents an emotional and social commitment that can drive long-term growth, market penetration, and resilience against competitors, underscoring its greater strategic importance in brand management.

Table 6: Direct and indirect effects of ARM on BL dimensions via HMO and UMO and CU.

	Coef.	T-statistics	P-values
Total effects			
ARM -> BA	0.508***	17.832	0.000
ARM -> CU	0.564***	19.680	0.000
ARM -> HMO	0.736***	29.200	0.000
ARM -> RI	0.429***	13.684	0.000
ARM -> RS	0.480***	17.093	0.000
ARM -> UMO	0.628***	20.714	0.000
CU -> BA	0.901***	95.266	0.000
CU -> RI	0.762***	27.258	0.000
CU -> RS	0.852***	57.933	0.000
HMO -> BA	0.273***	6.277	0.000
HMO -> CU	0.303***	6.337	0.000
HMO -> RI	0.231***	6.391	0.000
HMO -> RS	0.258***	6.254	0.000
UMO -> BA	0.488***	12.542	0.000
UMO -> CU	0.542***	12.771	0.000
UMO -> RI	0.413***	10.189	0.000
UMO -> RS	0.462***	12.302	0.000
Specific indirect effects			
HMO -> CU -> BA	0.273***	6.277	0.000
ARM -> UMO -> CU -> RS	0.290***	9.378	0.000
HMO -> CU -> RI	0.231***	6.391	0.000
UMO -> CU -> BA	0.488***	12.542	0.000
HMO -> CU -> RS	0.258***	6.254	0.000
ARM -> UMO -> CU -> RI	0.259***	8.128	0.000
UMO -> CU -> RI	0.413***	10.189	0.000
ARM -> HMO -> CU -> RI	0.170***	6.426	0.000
ARM -> UMO -> CU -> BA	0.307***	9.507	0.000
UMO -> CU -> RS	0.462***	12.302	0.000
ARM -> HMO -> CU -> RS	0.190***	6.301	0.000
ARM -> HMO -> CU -> BA	0.201***	6.332	0.000
ARM -> UMO -> CU	0.341***	9.762	0.000
ARM -> HMO -> CU	0.223***	6.411	0.000

SRMR		0.068
d_ULS		5.144
	R-square	R-square adjusted
RI	0.622	0.612
BA	0.557	0.448
RS	0.547	0.443

(***) reflects significance at 1%.

The findings indicate that the impact of utilitarian values mediated by reduced consumer uncertainty is strongest on resistance to switching, surpassing its influence on both repurchase intentions and brand advocacy. The primary value of a utilitarian product lies in its reliable performance and problem-solving capability. When uncertainty is reduced, it solidifies the consumer's perception of the brand as a dependable, low-risk solution, thereby creating significant barriers to considering alternatives, as the cognitive and perceived performance costs of switching become too high. In contrast, hedonic values, through the same mediating mechanism, exert a more pronounced effect on brand advocacy than on repurchase intentions or resistance to switching, highlighting the role of enjoyment and emotional satisfaction in motivating consumers to actively promote the brand. The emotional and social nature of hedonic consumption. Reducing uncertainty about a pleasurable product or experience doesn't just assure functionality; it validates the consumer's emotional investment and self-concept. This assurance transforms satisfaction into confidence, empowering and motivating the consumer to publicly endorse the brand to others, as advocacy becomes a way to share a positive identity and reinforce their own positive experience. These patterns align with prior research showing that functional benefits primarily stabilize consumer retention, whereas experiential and emotional factors drive proactive brand promotion (e.g., Hollebeek et al., 2014; Iglesias et al., 2019). While the literature often emphasizes hedonic and utilitarian drivers separately, the current results extend this understanding by demonstrating their differential mediated effects via reduced consumer uncertainty, confirming the nuanced roles these motivations play in shaping distinct brand loyalty outcomes. Figure 5 presents a summary of the factorial contributions and the effects of the various constructs on the dimensions of brand loyalty, including their relationships with repurchase intentions, brand advocacy, and resistance to switching.

Fig. 5. Structural model path coefficients for brand loyalty dimensions

5. CONCLUSION

This study provides robust evidence that augmented reality marketing significantly enhances brand loyalty through both hedonic and utilitarian values, with consumer uncertainty reduction playing a pivotal mediating role. The findings demonstrate that utilitarian values, emphasizing functional and practical benefits, exert stronger effects on reducing consumer uncertainty, resistance to switching, and overall loyalty compared to hedonic values. Conversely, hedonic values show the most pronounced influence on brand advocacy, highlighting the importance of emotional engagement and experiential satisfaction in driving proactive consumer behaviors. The mediating role of reduced consumer uncertainty is more substantial in the pathways linking utilitarian values to brand advocacy and resistance to switching than in pathways to repurchase intentions, indicating that confidence and trust amplify both retention and advocacy outcomes. The findings further reveal that

ARM positively impacts all three dimensions of brand loyalty, repurchase intentions, brand advocacy, and resistance to switching, with brand advocacy exhibiting the strongest coefficients. This underscores the strategic significance of advocacy over transactional loyalty, aligning with literature that emphasizes the social and emotional dimensions of proactive brand promotion. The study also confirms that utilitarian drivers are more effective in stabilizing consumer retention, while hedonic drivers more powerfully encourage advocacy behaviors, reflecting a nuanced interplay between functional and experiential motivations.

Collectively, these findings validate and extend existing research by demonstrating that combining functional benefits, enjoyable experiences, and reduced uncertainty fosters comprehensive loyalty outcomes. They suggest that marketing strategies integrating ARM should simultaneously address consumers' cognitive, affective, and confidence-based needs to maximize long-term loyalty, retention, and advocacy. The study thus contributes to theory by clarifying the differential pathways through which utilitarian and hedonic values operate and by highlighting the critical role of uncertainty reduction in enhancing both behavioral and attitudinal brand loyalty.

5.1. Managerial and policy implications

The findings of this study offer several actionable insights for managers seeking to leverage augmented reality marketing (ARM) to strengthen brand loyalty. First, the pronounced influence of ARM on both utilitarian and hedonic values suggests that marketers should design immersive experiences that simultaneously provide functional benefits, such as efficiency, reliability, and problem-solving capabilities, and enjoyable, emotionally engaging

experiences. Prioritizing functional aspects can reduce consumer uncertainty, thereby enhancing confidence and fostering long-term loyalty, while hedonic elements are particularly effective in stimulating brand advocacy. Second, the differential effects observed across loyalty dimensions indicate that managers should strategically align ARM initiatives with specific outcomes. Since brand advocacy demonstrated the strongest response to ARM, campaigns emphasizing engaging, shareable experiences are likely to generate more word-of-mouth promotion than merely reinforcing repurchase intentions or discouraging switching. This underscores the importance of integrating social and experiential elements into marketing strategies to transform satisfied customers into active brand ambassadors. Third, the mediating role of reduced consumer uncertainty highlights the value of reassuring customers about product reliability, performance, and consistency. Firms can achieve this by providing clear information, demonstrations, or interactive trials through augmented reality, thereby reducing perceived risks and increasing commitment to the brand. Moreover, the stronger effect of utilitarian values in mitigating uncertainty and enhancing resistance to switching suggests that emphasizing practical benefits is crucial in highly competitive or high-risk purchase contexts. Finally, these insights reinforce the need for a balanced approach that combines cognitive (utilitarian) and affective (hedonic) appeals. Managers should consider ARM not only as a tool for immediate engagement but also as a mechanism to build confidence, reduce perceived risks, and cultivate advocacy-driven loyalty. By aligning AR-based initiatives with both functional and emotional consumer needs, firms can enhance overall brand performance and foster sustainable competitive advantages.

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